

Joint response to the Genesis Mission RFI from the
Alliance for Data Science and AI (ADSA) and the
United States Research Software Engineer Association (US-RSE)
Full Version

Organizations:

The [Alliance for Data Science and AI](#) is a professional association advancing responsible and inclusive data science and AI in academic research, education, and training. We connect institutions and individuals to collectively shape the future of the field, ensuring that ethical and societal considerations remain at the forefront. **Contact: Micaela Parker, Founder and Executive Director, micaela@alliance4datascience.ai**

The [United States Research Software Engineer Association \(US-RSE\)](#) is a national professional organization and community-driven association advancing the recognition, professionalization, and impact of Research Software Engineers across academia, National Laboratories, and industry. US-RSE connects institutions and individuals to strengthen sustainable software practices, support workforce development, and ensure that AI and advanced computing technologies are responsibly integrated into the scientific enterprise. **Contact: Sandra Gesing, Executive Director, sandra@us-rse.org**

Executive Summary

AI may be the most transformative technology of this generation, potentially enabling significant acceleration of scientific discovery and societal benefits at a scale far beyond what humans alone can achieve. The Genesis Mission’s ambition to train 100,000 scientists and engineers in AI over the next decade through coordinated initiatives that treat AI technology and competency as foundational is commendable. The workforce demands of a scalable AI-powered innovation ecosystem will encompass the full lifecycle of AI development and implementation, covering data, models, and compute, as well as application by domain-specific practitioners seeking to amplify their work with AI tools. **As stewards and operators of these building blocks of a robust AI ecosystem, and as educators of an emerging AI-enabled scientific workforce, Data Scientists (DSs) and Research Software Engineers (RSEs) are key stakeholders in achieving this ambitious goal, acting as essential workforce multipliers who operationalize AI into sustained scientific infrastructure.** As major U.S.-based professional societies for DSs and RSEs, ADSA and US-RSE are providing this Response to ensure a strong and continuous partnership between our organizations, Federal decision-makers, and the sectors in which much of this emerging workforce will eventually operate. Through this Response and the ongoing dialogue it sparks, ADSA and US-RSE will continue to advocate for dedicated investment in educating those who engineer, steward, and implement AI systems across their lifecycle. Engaging in this dialogue will ensure that the next generation of these

professionals is shaped in collaboration, rather than competition, with other sectors for talent and resources, including those made available through the Genesis Mission. Importantly, our organizations represent institutional and individual members from academia, industry, and National Laboratories, positioning us as strategic enablers of the dual-competency education and training envisioned by the Mission.

In responding to the individual questions listed below, we wish to emphasize four cross-cutting points regarding the education and training components of the Genesis Mission:

- **AI's impacts are society-level, and AI education and training should reflect this.** The Genesis Mission and the educational programs and resources it supports must be designed intentionally to benefit all of society, not only a small set of institutions, companies, or individuals. Long term, AI could power an accelerated R&D enterprise that yields extraordinary abundance, but it could also intensify inequality and economic stratification if access and benefits become concentrated. The Mission should explicitly aim to broaden participation and distribute capacity across geographies, institution types, demographics, and economic resource levels.
- **Utilize cross-sectoral collaboration to advance education and training.** Education is the acquisition and mastery of knowledge and critical thinking, while training is the development of specific skills and competencies for task-oriented use. By fortifying partnerships between academic institutions (for traditional education) and industry and National Laboratories (for experiential training), the Genesis Mission can leverage the expertise of DSs and RSEs across these settings to equip trainees at all levels (undergraduate through postdoctoral) with the interdisciplinary knowledge and practical skills needed to bridge AI and other scientific and engineering disciplines.
- **Dual competency is necessary but not sufficient.** It is critical to note that there is a difference between a student educated in two parallel competencies and a student with dual competency. A student who completes an AI course and a science course has two parallel competencies; a student who uses AI to carry out a scientific research project while understanding the limitations of the AI approach has dual competencies. While a dual-competency learning approach can help address the training challenge of developing competency in both AI and a scientific discipline, a critical third competency must also be addressed: the cognitive skills required to work effectively as a *human-AI team*. As AI becomes increasingly incorporated across the research lifecycle, scientists need to know when an AI output is reliable, when to override it, and how to maintain independent judgment when AI-generated solutions are fluent and confident but inaccurate, or, in the worst case, potentially harmful. In other words, developing AI competency should ensure that humans are in the lead, not just in the loop. Thus, education and training efforts supported by the Mission should pair technical training in AI with normative training around accuracy and transparency, privacy and security, scientific integrity, and ethical use. Without competency in responsible, human-centered

AI, the Mission risks producing scientists who can operate AI tools but cannot recognize or proceed when those tools fail or pose unacceptable risk.

- **AI is simultaneously the subject of training and a disruptive force on the training pipeline.** AI is altering the traditional training pipeline for science and technology careers by compressing the entry-level tasks that have historically served as foundations for developing scientific expertise. At the same time, AI systems must be constructed as maintainable assets for optimal deployment, creating new demand for competencies such as provenance tracking, reproducible workflow orchestration, and IoT integration. Just as these features must be engineered into AI systems by design, so should the training supported by the Genesis Mission incorporate these practices from the beginning. The Mission must address how AI changes the nature of workforce development, not just the technical content of curricula. If not, the Mission risks building a pipeline suited to a bygone labor market.

Through resource provision, partnership building, real-world learning, and targeted mentorship across all education levels, the Genesis Mission can leverage the expertise and experience of DSs and RSEs to systematize these principles in scientific training and practice, advancing the Mission's vision of a productive AI-enabled R&D workforce that serves as the backbone of a vibrant discovery-driven economy.

Responses to Individual Questions

1. How can DOE catalyze research collaborations between DOE National Laboratories, universities, and industry to meet the goals of the Genesis program?

DOE can catalyze effective collaborations by providing access to its unique cadre of enabling resources and clear pathways for impact that reach students across diverse academic settings.

This includes:

- **Resource enablement (infrastructure):** offer funding and enable access to high-performance computing/specialized compute resources that most universities and research groups don't have locally. Compute resources include CPUs, GPUs, TPUs, DPUs, IFPGAs, strong (terabytes/second) networking resources, and exabyte storage for use by institutions with a range of research intensities.
- **Resource enablement (training):** offer funding and enable access to multimodal training resources covering the breadth of experience and subject matter domains (including data science and software engineering) that underlie AI theory and application.
- **Operational partnerships:** leverage existing federal grand challenge mechanisms (moonshots, prize challenges, hackathons) to focus and support collaborations between universities, industry, and National Labs on well-defined scopes and deliverables, particularly those with high impact for scientific discovery, national security, and energy innovation.
- **Clear upward pipeline for discoveries:** researchers should feel there is a real channel to communicate insights and breakthroughs upward, learned from, and applied by DOE and other federal stakeholders. Collaboration works best when participants can see how results translate into broader outcomes and impact.
- **Targeted training opportunities across institution types:** because ~40% of all undergraduates are enrolled at community colleges, provide internship opportunities at DOE National Labs and other DOE research facilities in a clearly defined partnership arrangement for community college students. Promote this initiative so that students can easily take advantage of the opportunity.

2. How can DOE incentivize partnerships between universities, DOE National Laboratories, industry, and philanthropic organizations to 1) establish new training paths for bachelor's and master's degrees focused on dual competencies in AI and scientific/engineering disciplines and 2) provide innovative experiences to prepare doctoral students and post-doctoral associates for careers in AI for science?

For nearly two decades, the DS and RSE communities have been delivering education and training programs at the interface between domain-specific knowledge and domain-agnostic computational and data science skills. This body of experience has revealed strategic

optimization points for interdisciplinary training in these fields that can serve as key targets for the Genesis Mission’s educational objectives, including:

- **Competency integration, not co-existence:** a student who completes an AI course and a science course has two parallel competencies; a student who uses AI to carry out a scientific research project while understanding the limitations of the AI approach has *dual* competencies. DOE-led partnerships should support the latter: research and educational experiences where AI is embedded in scientific practice, not appended as a parallel component. This change in curriculum design will not be simple, and will require resources to support faculty and other instructors - resources that many institutions do not currently have budget lines for.
- **Cross-sector competency frameworks:** define competency profiles for AI-for-science roles at all degree levels, through collaboration among government, non-profit, academic, and industry stakeholders. Competency profiles offer academia with concrete targets for program development, provide employers with a shared vocabulary for describing hiring needs, and enable all stakeholders to integrate new technological advances. The Genesis Mission can lead the way, by incorporating lessons learned by the Intelligence Community (IC) to develop a competency resource guide for Data Science and to structure cross-sectoral experiential learning using the IC’s Joint Duty Assignment model.
- **Co-designed curricula + experiences:** fund consortia where National Labs, universities, and industry jointly define what “dual competency” means in practice, then build programs around those outcomes that incorporate cross-disciplinary mentorship. ADSA has more than a decade of experience in dual-mentored doctoral and postdoctoral training programs, while US-RSE is building mentorship programs to foster professional development in scientific domains that require research software.
- **Experiential opportunities embedded into programs:** as part of the degree path, require or incentivize real-world education and training experiences involving hands-on contributions to high-impact projects. Hands-on contributions could be done through grants and collaboration opportunities that foster this kind of training and programming.
- **Clear career pathways:** for all students and learners, partnerships should include mentorship and visibility into what the job looks like at National Labs, academia, and industry, so training aligns with fundamental roles. DOE should incentivize rotational or other time-limited experiences across sectors that allow trainees to spend meaningful periods working at National Labs and/or with industry data, bringing a cross-sectoral perspective to their academic settings.
- **Tool access as infrastructure:** provide funding or other mechanisms to ensure students and researchers have reliable access to high-capability AI tools (not just free tiers). In practice, this could include model access/subscriptions and/or research-use credits.

3. What attributes might attract undergraduates to programs that offer dual competency degrees?

Programs that are financially accessible, have clear connections to meaningful career paths, and connect AI skills to solutions for real-world problems will attract undergraduates. Such programs would include:

- **Financial incentives:** similar to the NSA's National Centers of Academic Excellence in Cybersecurity (NCAE-C) program, DOE can provide funding to cover the tuition, fees, and other expenses of dual-competency students.
- **Real research problems:** students are motivated when education feels like a direct ramp into solving something tangible and impactful, rather than abstract coursework disconnected from application.
- **Modernized learning models for future-proof careers:** AI is changing the learning landscape. Chatbots/agents can dramatically lower the barrier to entry for starting research-like work before complete mastery. Educational programs should embrace this while still valuing what universities uniquely provide: community, mentorship, collaboration, and social learning. Programs that endow students with highly transferable skills and frame AI competency as a source of professional agency (learning to direct and evaluate AI rather than compete with it) will attract students who might otherwise avoid STEM fields out of concern that "AI will take my job." The message should be that these programs prepare researchers who know how to appropriately deploy AI tools, evaluate them for bias and error, and explain their use to stakeholders.

4. Beyond funding, what other opportunities could DOE, including its National Laboratories and user facilities, bring to these partnerships?

DOE can leverage its vast network of labs, facilities, and experts to provide resource access and opportunities for mentorship, engagement, and professional development across two- and four-year academic institutions, including:

- **Compute + facilities access:** practical access to National Lab user facilities, specialized datasets, and high-performance computing environments.
- **High-quality mentorship and exposure:** structured opportunities for students to interact with National Lab scientists and engineers, including facilitated mentorship, shadowing, and intensive, on-site and virtual workshops.
- **Curriculum co-design and advising:** collaboration among DOE researchers, industry stakeholders, and academic faculty to develop applied curricula (e.g., problem sets based on real-world problems) can help bridge the gap between learning outcomes and workforce needs.
- **Professional development resources and events for faculty:** faculty need professional development opportunities to learn how to use AI in their own research and, importantly, to teach AI and its breadth of applications in advanced topics courses in their disciplines.

5. In addition to classroom and research training, what other contributions could universities make to support these partnerships?

Universities can serve a multifaceted role as enablers, coordinators, and mutual beneficiaries of partnerships that translate dual-competency education and training into real-world impact. These facets include:

- **Talent identification and facilitation:** university faculty are uniquely poised to identify strong talent among their students. Faculty could use cross-sectoral relationships supported by the Mission to connect top students to internship, apprenticeship, and post-graduation employment opportunities in industry and National Labs. On top of this, DOE could leverage its university partners through the Mission to stand up and administer a "rising stars" program for promising dual competency-trained students.
- **Stackable real-world training:** analogous to medical residencies, universities can develop and manage programs that translate classroom and research training directly into real-world roles with increasing independence and problem complexity. With DOE support, academic institutions can standardize and administer career exploration programs involving rotations, internships, and apprenticeships with National Labs and companies that embody this progressive autonomy structure.
- **Bidirectional resource sharing:** building off of Mission-enabled resource sharing with academic partners (see response to Question 1), universities can similarly share their unique resources (e.g., data assets, subject matter expertise) with partners in industry and National Labs, creating a virtuous cycle of collaboration built on shared digital and human resources.
- **Translational deliverables:** the outputs of dual-competency training may carry commercialization or other intellectual property potential. Universities can bring this potential to fruition through industry-sponsored research, patenting and tech transfer, small business grants, and venture creation and incubation.
- **Scaffolded mentorship:** transcending the boundaries of traditional one-on-one mentoring, the Mission can support mentorship that allows students to learn end-to-end R&D workflows from experts at each stage of the pipeline. Universities can make essential contributions to this mentorship framework by engaging mentors across academic departments and research centers, as well as through their alumni networks.
- **Professional socialization:** In addition to imparting subject matter knowledge and cultivating domain-specific skills, universities serve a central role in inculcating "soft skills" for the future workforce. The importance of this role will only grow as AI's ability to convey "hard" knowledge continues to burgeon in educational settings.

6. Beyond funding, what types of contributions could industry and philanthropic organizations make to enhance these partnerships and enrich the experiences of the students?

Industry and philanthropic organizations can add value by contributing sector-specific expertise and mentorship, and by supporting project-based training for students by furnishing projects grounded in authentic, real-world contexts that allow students to reap tangible benefits beyond the knowledge and skills they gain. These organizations can ensure:

- **Tangible value to students:** beyond the benefits of training for cultivating knowledge and skills, companies and organizations can ensure that students who participate in experiential learning realize direct, tangible benefits, such as compensation for work performed, preservation of intellectual property rights, and the ability to share their portfolio of work with future employers by prioritizing projects whose details and outputs can be disclosed.
- **Real-world project exposure:** companies and organizations can furnish projects with the potential for real impact and, conversely, that are impacted by real-world constraints (security, reliability, maintainability, deployment), helping students learn beyond contrived prototypes in the classroom.
- **Career visibility and targeted mentorship:** help students understand the landscape of roles at the AI–science intersection and offer sector-specific mentorship for students committed to, or with interest in, exploring industry and philanthropic careers.
- **Professional development for educators:** provide faculty with opportunities and training to build sector-specific knowledge and skills they can then integrate into their pedagogy and curricula.

7. In addition to AI, which scientific and engineering disciplines are well-suited for this dual competency training approach?

Although specific disciplines listed below are natural fits as part of AI dual competency training, answering this question thoroughly should take a broad view to encompass any discipline in which (a) AI tools are powerful but require domain judgment to apply correctly, and (b) mathematical foundations provide the basis for understanding what AI systems are doing. The common thread should be disciplines where AI augments human reasoning rather than replacing it, and where the consequences of uncritical AI use are significant. Generally, dual competency would be most impactful in disciplines that are data-rich, computationally intensive, or operationally time-sensitive, where AI can accelerate discovery workflows, literature synthesis, software/tool development, and analysis pipelines.

Research Software Engineering and Data Science represent applied, research-integrated professions distinct from traditional computer science. While computer science advances theory and algorithms, RSEs and DSs focus on production-grade scientific software, data architectures, workflow systems, and computational environments embedded directly within

active research programs across sectors. Their expertise lies in **translating computational innovation into reliable, scalable research and production capacity**. Recognizing this distinction is essential when designing dual-competency programs intended to prepare graduates for operational AI-for-Science roles.

Specific disciplines under this umbrella include, but are not limited to:

- Data Science (including specialized programs such as Data Theory)
- Research Software Engineering
- Energy Systems Engineering
- Materials Science
- Biomedical Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Chemistry
- Physics
- Computational Biology/Bioinformatics
- Engineering
- Earth/Environmental/Climate Science (e.g., hazard detection, forecasting)
- Mathematics (pure and applied)
- Statistics
- Computer Science

Importantly, the Mission should not view this list as prescriptive or static. Due to AI's disruptive potential, the suitability of existing disciplines for AI integration may change over time, and new domains may emerge as AI capabilities expand. Educators must be equipped with the resources needed to maintain agility and responsiveness as science and engineering evolve for the foreseeable future.

8. What components are needed for an effective dual competency degree program to best prepare students for successful careers at the bachelor's level? At the master's level?

At both levels, the core of such a program would be a strong foundation in a scientific domain, plus AI fundamentals (theory and practice), brought together in an integrated curriculum that provides ample opportunities to apply both sets of competencies simultaneously to solve real problems. These programs should incorporate a pedagogical approach that teaches students to use AI as a collaborative reasoning tool while maintaining accountability for the quality and correctness of their work. This means teaching students to articulate their reasoning to AI systems, to cultivate reasonable skepticism about AI outputs, and to demonstrate core competencies independent of AI assistance.

Key components for **bachelor's programs** include:

- Fundamentals of the scientific/engineering discipline
- Foundational mathematical literacy (e.g., linear algebra, probability, optimization)
- Practical AI literacy: what modern AI systems are, what they can and cannot do, and how to use them responsibly
- AI-assisted reasoning: how to formulate problems for AI tools, how to interact effectively with these tools (e.g., prompt engineering), how to evaluate AI-generated solutions, and how to recognize AI limitations, bias, failure modes (e.g., hallucinations), and conflicts with established domain knowledge
- Project-based experiences in which students use AI to solve domain problems in a semi-structured way
- Assessments that require students to demonstrate both AI fluency and independent scientific judgment, rather than (or in addition to) traditional exams

Key components for **master's programs** include:

- Deeper domain specialization and more advanced computational methods
- More depth on how AI systems work (conceptually and practically), including the limitations of specific model architectures for specific scientific questions, as well as
- Combining the theory and practice of how AI tools, workflows, and multi-agent systems
- Stronger emphasis on building functional, secure, and maintainable research software and pipelines
- Larger, more open-ended projects that mirror real research/industry needs
- Communication skills to bridge AI-technical and domain-specialist communities

Both levels of training would maximize recruitment and retention of top talent by offering financial incentives (e.g., scholarships, paid internships/experiential learning), which the Mission can support through grantmaking or other funding processes.

9. What components are needed to prepare graduate students and post-doctoral students for successful careers at the nexus of AI and science?

To prepare graduate and postdoctoral students for successful careers at the nexus of AI and science, training should continue to focus on core scientific fundamentals by adding **three primary components**: operational mastery of AI-assisted research workflows, fundamentals of responsible and professional software engineering, and explicit ethics, norms, and integrity training.

Training should focus on **how to use AI-assisted research workflows** for unambiguous tasks that accelerate workflows, such as literature review, code development, and rapid software prototyping. Training should focus on:

- developing rigorous verification habits, such as grounding models (Model Context Protocol), verifying sources, verifying code outputs, and ensuring that speed does not come at the cost of accuracy.
- Developing skills in exploratory data analysis and learning how to critically evaluate how the inputs (the data) are affecting the outputs of AI models
- **teaching professional software engineering standards and practices** focused on understanding unit testing, security, maintainability, reproducibility, and scientific integrity, as these are essential for building trustworthy AI-enabled scientific systems.

In parallel, training should also set clear **guidance and expectations for the ethical use of AI in science**. Training should focus on:

- Educating trainees on how not to use AI (generating publications, spreading deception or misinformation, laundering unverified claims into the literature, etc.)
- How to identify societal stakes and risks that may come from specific AI use cases.
- The context of the scientific domain in which the AI is being applied, because the “societal stakes” and misuse risks are often domain-specific.
- Training should focus on how **to spot risk, escalate or seek review, and document choices**.

The following training requirements ensure that AI ethics becomes an operational part of core scientific fundamental training rather than an abstract module.

10. How could partnerships between DOE, universities, and industry provide new training opportunities for students to best prepare them for private and public sector jobs?

Partnerships between DOE, universities, and industry would provide trainees with the context and skills needed to integrate into non-academic sector jobs. Programs should expose trainees to the norms, constraints, and opportunities of these sectors rather than solely train them for the academic pipeline. Graduate students and postdocs would benefit from programs that explicitly prepare them for careers in:

- National labs
- Industry
- Government agencies

Partnerships between DOE, universities, and industry can create new training opportunities that prepare students for both private- and public-sector jobs by giving them authentic, mentored work experience under real constraints. Examples of this include, but are not limited to:

- Joint projects that mimic real-world workflows (including security and quality expectations)
- Mentorship from practicing professionals (national labs + industry)

- Access to tooling and compute environments they'll use on the job
- Providing visibility into role expectations and career paths across public and private sectors through apprenticeships and rotations

In practice, this could pair students with a practicing mentor in the private or public sector so they understand how work is executed and reviewed, all while gaining hands-on experience in directly relevant tooling and computing environments and understanding the expectations of that career. Instead of parallel coordination structures, the Mission could leverage existing organizational programs such as:

- ADSA: functions as a coordinating organization for data science education across academia, government, and industry, with convening power and support for curriculum development, and has access to channels for piloting and scaling shared best practices through its network of member academic institutions.
- Existing government-funded fellowships: Programs such as the AAAS Science and Technology Policy Fellowship have a strong history of recruiting and retaining PhD-level talent in government and provide clear avenues for transitioning academics into private- and public-sector jobs.

Continued funding and the creation of similar government career-entry programs that begin at the undergraduate/graduate levels would allow students to transition into private- and public-sector jobs more easily.

It is important to note that, at a high level, it's also helpful to treat "training" as distinct from "education": universities primarily deliver education, while partnerships can provide training through additional labs and applied projects. (Though it is important to emphasize that many academic campuses offer informal training, such as through the Libraries, extension offices, and data science and AI institutes.) This has two complementary implications: creating more hands-on lab and project time for students is fundamentally a resource question for partners, while ensuring students can include AI in their learning journeys, thought processes, critical thinking, and deeper understanding of the capabilities of new technologies in their fields is a resource question for formal education in academia.

11. What type of experiential opportunities are needed to complement classroom instruction to best prepare students for future jobs?

Practical experiential learning can take many forms, and ideally, individual students could engage in various complementary types of experiential learning at different stages of their education and training. Specific examples include:

- **Practice AI tools** in realistic contexts to learn good habits for verification, documentation, and input/output quality assessment.

- **Shadowing and mentorship** with practicing researchers/engineers, including those at National Labs and in industry.
- **Project-based collaborations, including paid internships** in which students make hands-on contributions to authentic research applications.
- **Externships for faculty** to bring back real-world knowledge and skills that will benefit their students in the classroom.

Although “experiential” tends to evoke real-world settings, an equally valuable experiential resource for mastering AI competency would be **structured learning tools focused on AI-augmented scientific reasoning**, not as a procedural exercise, but as a mode of active learning. Rather than providing answers, such tools can ask students to articulate their reasoning, challenge their assumptions, and redirect when they seek shortcuts. The Mission should fund the development and rigorous evaluation of such tools across relevant dual-competency disciplines. Critically, educators and the Mission should design these tools around explicit pedagogical principles rather than deploy them as generic AI tutoring systems. The difference matters: an AI tutor optimizes for answer delivery, while a **thought partner optimizes for students’ capacity to reason independently** in conditions that mirror actual scientific practice.

12. How many American bachelor’s and master’s degree students could be trained in a steady state program at your institution? How could the program be scaled across the nation?

Estimates of the total student populations across all of ADSA’s and US-RSE’s 68 academic member institutions in the U.S.:

- Undergraduate enrollment: ~1,400,000+
- Graduate enrollment: ~470,000+

In addition to providing quantitative estimates, it is valuable to note what we believe would be required. At a minimum, scaling nationwide will depend on:

- **Resource access:** reliable access to capable AI tools (not just free tiers), plus compute where needed
- **Portable learning resources:** shared foundational curriculum components and experiential modules that different types of institutions (e.g., R1, R2, community college) can adopt and modify
- **Equity-by-design:** ensuring that Mission-supported initiatives do not disproportionately benefit institutions that are already well-resourced and build in mechanisms that intentionally uplift under-resourced learning environments
- **Faculty and workforce capacity:** expanded hiring and sustained support for faculty, and instructional and technical staff with AI-for-Science expertise who can train, mentor,

and embed AI practices within disciplinary programs. The Genesis Mission cannot succeed without a significant investment in new university faculty and staff.

Training individuals alone will not be sufficient to achieve Genesis's goals. Institutions must also develop durable academic and laboratory capacity to support AI-for-Science infrastructure, research software engineering, and computational workforce development. Without sufficient faculty and professional staff embedded in mission-relevant programs, training efforts may remain episodic rather than systemic. DOE can play an important role by incentivizing institutional models that integrate AI expertise, research software engineering, and scientific computing into long-term research and education structures.

13. How could community colleges and other educational institutions contribute and be included in this pipeline?

Community colleges directly award a substantial proportion of degrees in domains relevant to dual-competency AI training. Students from these institutions frequently feed into bachelor's and advanced degree programs, with about 40% of undergraduates starting at community colleges. Moreover, community colleges serve a disproportionate share of first-generation, rural, working, and mid-career learners compared to four-year institutions. If the Genesis Mission does not intentionally integrate community colleges and community-based learning into its education and training strategy, it risks reinforcing structural inequities rather than broadening participation in AI-enabled science, which is essential to achieving the Mission at a national scale. ADSA and US-RSE can serve the Mission in this capacity by identifying specific AI infrastructure needs and brokering partnerships between community colleges and resource-rich institutions that focus on:

- **AI infrastructure sharing:** if the Mission's training programs depend on commercial AI tools, high-performance computing access, or expensive software subscriptions, community college students will be excluded in practice even if included in principle. DOE should ensure that Mission-funded training resources (including AI tools, datasets, and computing environments) are made accessible to community college programs, either directly or through four-year university partners.
- **Foundational AI literacy:** community colleges are well-positioned to introduce foundational AI literacy, data stewardship, and computational workflow concepts within their applied STEM programs, which can then be carried into the workforce or flow upward into four-year and advanced degree programs. The Mission can provide resources to community colleges to support and grow these foundational programs.
- **Applied AI fellowships:** DOE can establish an Applied AI Fellowship track specifically for students from community colleges. Fellows can participate in structured summer or year-long placements at National Laboratories, working under joint supervision from laboratory mentors and academic faculty to contribute to real-world research projects employing AI solutions.

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- **Support for informal training:** beyond degree-granting programs, there are a host of informal training opportunities available for professional development and upskilling in AI and related scientific domains, including online courses, community-based training events, and domain-specific professional development programs offered by scientific societies, National Laboratories, and federally supported research institutions.. There is potential for high impact and return on investment from these learning pathways, but their quality, approaches, outcomes, and availability are not standardized. The Mission can strengthen these informal training modalities by providing resources, bringing organizations together to foster new informal learning partnerships, and incentivizing benchmarks for training quality and outcomes.

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